

TREASURE

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*Title: Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research
Training of Early Stage Researchers: a Pilot Study*

Training program: List of trainings and resources to support implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research Deliverable D.3

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Description version 1.0	This document includes the list of training programs and resources identified to support the implementation of the previously outlined practices and outputs in the TREASURE project deliverable D.2 (DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785597) following assessment and gap analysis of training available at the University of Coimbra (UC) (Milestone M.3). The resources here listed concern education and training programs existing either at UC or available resources from external sites, whenever gaps were identified within UC.

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¹Contributor roles follow the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT), <https://credit.niso.org/> .

List of Abbreviations

RROR *Reproducible, reusable and open research*

UC *University of Coimbra*

TER *Training Events and Resources*

TREASURE *Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research Training of Early Stage Researchers*

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Table 2 *List of external resources identified to support the training and implementation of RROR practices and outputs included in TREASURE program, categorized into resource types (i.e. course units within 1st, 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; certified training; workshops; summer schools; modules, seminars, and advanced courses within 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; toolkits; other resources).*

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1. Introduction

1.1. Context and aims

Context

This document concerns the development and implementation of the TREASURE program (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/>) in the University of Coimbra (UC) that aims to *enable* the implementation and adoption of more **reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR)** principles, practices and outputs across disciplines and it is applicable to all areas of knowledge, starting at earlier stages of research - master and doctoral research studies.

The deliverable document D.3 results from the TREASURE project *Task 4 - Training assessment and gap analysis*, and follows the previous Milestone M.3 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17078623>) in which the methodology to identify institutional resources was detailed.

Aims

The current document, Deliverable D.3, compiles and presents both **institutional** (available at UC) and **external** training **resources** to support the TREASURE **training program** and its participating **students** in the implementation of RROR practices and/or outputs in their research theses, covering different disciplines whenever possible.

The resources connect directly with the practices and outputs currently included in the TREASURE program (**Figure 1**; Deliverable D.2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785597>).

This task was performed in collaboration with both institutional (TREASURE local advisory board; vice-rectory for culture, communication and open science; other relevant UC members) and external stakeholders (TREASURE external advisory board; other expert external members).

PRACTICES	OUTPUTS
<i>(may include or result in Outputs)</i>	<i>(should: have a persistent identifier, be accessible in a trusted repository)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contribution statements • Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps • Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies • Unique Identifiers for research materials/resources • Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science or Participatory research • Science communication, dissemination, policy recommendations [activities, materials, policy briefs] • Reporting of null results • Reporting guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preregistration or Study design plans • Registered reports • Open step-by-step methods and protocols • Data sharing • Open source code and software • Open/reusable materials/resources • Preprints • Open Educational materials

Figure 1. List of the reproducible, reusable, and open research practices and outputs currently included in the TREASURE program (adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786585>).

2. Training program: list of resources available to support the identified reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs

2.1. Inclusion criteria

As stated before in Milestone M.3, to be included in Deliverable D.3 as training resource, the following inclusion criteria would need to verify:

- 1) the resource refers to training that **supports** the implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) **practices or outputs**, namely those included in the TREASURE D.2 Deliverable (**Figure 1**),
- 2) the source, platform for training delivery or trainer, is **trustworthy**, and/or holds **credentials** adequate to deliver the training (this criterion is hard to verify, but was based mainly on recommendations from research communities and/or experts),

- 3) the resource is **openly and freely available**, at least for master's and PhD candidates, or available through a registry or access protocol that holds no costs.

In the next sections, training resources – institutional (2.2.) or external (2.3.) – respecting these criteria are presented.

2.2. Institutional training resources (available at the University of Coimbra)

As a result of the exercise presented in Milestone M.3, *institutional* resources were identified and are listed in **Table 1**.

Resources coming from projects coordinated by UC or in which UC is a participating institution (such as BioData.pt, Re.Data and TRIPLE) were considered as internal resources.

Table 1. Institutional training resources identified for each RROR practice and output included in TREASURE program, categorized into resource types (i.e. course units within 1st, 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; certified training; workshops; summer schools; modules, seminars, and advanced courses within 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; toolkits; other resources).

PRACTICE OR OUTPUT	NUMBER OF RESOURCES IDENTIFIED & TYPE	RESOURCE TYPE
Author contribution statements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part I [link] [program link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	<p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Advanced course</p> <p>Advanced course</p>
Using evidence synthesis techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module on systematic reviews - PhD in Psychology (FPCEUC) 	Module in course unit
Preregistration or Study design plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part I [link] [program link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	<p>Advanced course</p> <p>Advanced course</p>
Registered Reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part I [link] [program link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	<p>Advanced course</p> <p>Advanced course</p>

Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies	(UC staff with expertise in RROR will provide materials)	
Open step-by-step methods and protocols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Re.Data project training] Workshop on Electronic notebooks, 2nd edition (UM, 11/12/2025) [registration link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part I [link] [program link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	Certified course Advanced course Advanced course
Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • Ciência Cidadã na UC: atividade de cocriação [EN: <i>Citizen science at UC: co-creation activity</i>] (IIIUC; Formações iiiUC: Ferramentas de Apoio à Investigação, 2024.01.30) [link] 	Module in course unit Course unit Workshop
Open materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • [TRIPLE project outputs] Francesca Di Donato, Lottie Provost, Tiziana Lombardo, Michela Vignoli, Stefanie Pohle, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Yin Chen, & Emilie Blotière. (2022). TRIPLE Training Toolkit (3.0). Zenodo [DOI] 	Course unit Course unit Course unit Toolkit
Unique and Persistent Identifiers for research materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part I [link] [program link] • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	Course unit Course unit Advanced course Advanced course
Open source code and software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thesis - course unit (PhD in Informatics Engineering, FCTUC/DEI, 2025/26) [link] • Introdução ao Github, gestão de projeto, e trabalho colaborativo [EN: <i>Introduction to GitHub, project management, and collaborative work</i>] (IIIUC; Formações iiiUC: Ferramentas de Apoio à Investigação, 2024.02.29) [link] 	Course unit Workshop

<p>Data sharing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thesis project (includes definition of Research Data Management plans (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link]) • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • BioData.pt: Research Data Management (RDM) (UC, 2025.10.09-10) [link to registration] • [LUMEN project course] semantic artefact ontology, FAIRification (online, 2025.09.04) [link to registration] • [Re.Data project training] Research Data Management (RDM), 2nd edition (UC, 2025.10.03) [link to registration] • [Re.Data project training] Research Data Management (RDM) – train the trainer workshop (IPB, 2025.11.25-26) [link to registration] • [Re.Data project training] Research Data Management (RDM), 3rd edition (UM, 2025.12.12) [link to registration] • [Re.Data project training] Legal questions, data protection, and licensing (ISCTE, 2025.10.26) [link to registration] • Research Data Management: Introduction and Basic Concepts (Advanced courses in Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices (Part I) - Doctoral program Experimental Biology and Biomedicine (IIIUC, CNC-UC/CIBB, 28/11/2024) [link]) • Repositórios Científicos: Estudo Geral e Zenodo [EN: <i>Scientific open repositories: Estudo Geral and Zenodo</i>] (IIIUC, Formações iiiUC - Ferramentas de apoio à Investigação, 2024.11.07) [link] • Licenças Creative Commons [EN: <i>Creative Commons licenses</i>] (IIIUC; Formações iiiUC: Ferramentas de Apoio à Investigação, 2025.02.06) [link] • [outputs from project TRIPLE] FAIR Data in Social Sciences and Humanities [link] [slides] [video recording] [Full Learning Resource on DARIAH-Campus] • [UC collaboration article] Wikidata for botanists - Sabine von Mering, Siobhan Leachman, Joaquim Santos, Heidi M Meudt, Wikidata for botanists: benefits of collaborating and sharing Linked Open Data, <i>Annals of Botany</i>, 2025, mcdf062 [DOI] 	<p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Certified training Workshop</p> <p>Certified training</p> <p>Certified training</p> <p>Certified training</p> <p>Certified training</p> <p>Certified training</p> <p>Module in advanced course</p> <p>Workshop</p> <p>Workshop</p> <p>Toolkit</p> <p>Article</p>
<p>Reporting of null results</p>	<p>(UC staff with expertise in RROR will provide materials)</p>	

Reporting guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	Advanced course
Preprints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDBEB Experimental Research Design & Responsible Research Practices - Part II [link] [program link] 	Advanced course
Science communication, public engagement, policy briefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication in Science (seminars) (2025/2026, PhD in Information Science, FLUC) [link] • Science communication (2025/2026, Master in Artificial Intelligence FCTUC/DEI) [link] • Comunicar Ciência Médica à Sociedade [EN: <i>Communicating medical science to society</i>] (FMUC, 1st cycle) [link] • Scientific Research and Science Communication (2025/26, Integrated Master in Pharmaceutical Sciences, FFUC) [link] • Science Decoder (SciComm challenge) (co-organized by FCTUC/DQuímica (talks and workshops, 2 days, 05.04.2024) [link] • Science Communication Module (2025/26, within Research Methodologies in Computational Media Design, PhD in Computational Media Design, IIIUC) [link] • Science Communication Module (2025/26, within Science, Education & Culture, PhD in History of Science and Science Education, IIIUC) [link] • Science Communication Module (2025/26, within Curricular Unit of Transversal Research Skills, PhD in Psychology, FPCEUC) [link] 	<p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Course unit</p> <p>Event</p> <p>Module in course unit</p> <p>Module in course unit</p> <p>Module in course unit</p>
Open educational resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [TRIPLE project outputs] TRIPLE training Toolkit: 5-step workflow to organize FAIR-by-design events and share training materials as Open Educational Resources (includes reproducible templates that trainers can reuse and adapt to their needs) [zenodo link] [page link] 	Toolkit

Legend: **DEI**, Informatics Engineering Department; **EN**, English; **FAIR**, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data principles; **FCTUC**, Faculty of Science and Technology, UC; **FFUC**, Faculty of Pharmacy, UC; **FLUC**, Faculty of Arts and Humanities, UC; **FPCEUC**, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, UC; **IIIUC or iiiuc**, Institute for Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra; **ISCTE-IUL**, ISCTE - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa; **LUMEN**, Linked User-Driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network; **PDBEB**, Doctoral (PhD) program in Biomedicine and Experimental Biology; **RDM**, Research Data Management; **RROR**, Reproducible, reusable and open research; **UC**, University of Coimbra; **UM**, University of Minho; **TRIPLE**, Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration.

2.2. External training resources

With the aim of *further supporting* the RROR practices and outputs included in the TREASURE program (**Figure 1**; Deliverable D.2, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785597>), and that could *offer additional disciplinary of study-type specific training*, external resources with quality recognized by RROR expert members were additionally identified. These are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2. List of external resources identified to support the training and implementation of RROR practices and outputs included in TREASURE program, categorized into resource types (i.e. course units within 1st, 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; certified training; workshops; summer schools; modules, seminars, and advanced courses within 2nd or 3rd cycle courses; toolkits; other resources).

PRACTICE OR OUTPUT	NUMBER OF RESOURCES IDENTIFIED & TYPE	RESOURCE TYPE
General resources: apply to two or more RROR practices and outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mind the GAP - Online training on research integrity (Module 3: this module includes information about Authorship, Research Data Management; Reporting results; Publication of Negative Results; Science communication; and Preprints) [link] 	Online course
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Turing Way online toolkit (covers topics of science communication, open source code, research data management, reproducible research, electronic lab notebooks, etc) [link] 	Toolkit
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FORRT: Syllabus for course "Understanding the Credibility Revolution and Open and Reproducible Research" [link to syllabus] 	Syllabus & resources
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sonja Bezzak, April Clyburne-Sherin, Philipp Conzett, Pedro Fernandes, Edit Görögh, Kerstin Helbig, Bianca Kramer, Ignasi Labastida, Kyle Niemeyer, Fotis Psomopoulos, Tony Ross-Hellauer, René Schneider, Jon Tennant, Ellen Verbakel, Helene Brinken, & Lambert Heller. (2018). Open Science Training Handbook (1.0) [Computer software]. Zenodo. [DOI Zenodo] [book online link] 	Toolkit / Online book
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [pathOS project output] S. Apartis, G. Catalano, G. Consiglio, R. Costas, E. Delugas, M. Dulong de Rosnay, I. Grypari, I. Karasz, Thomas Klebel, E. Kormann, N. Manola, H. Papageorgiou, E. Seminaroti, P. Stavropoulos, L. Stoy, V.A. Traag, T. van Leeuwen, T. Venturini, S. Vignetti, ... T. Willemse. (2025). Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook (1.0.1) [Computer software]. Zenodo. [DOI Zenodo] [Book online link] [direct link to open science indicators for different practices and outputs - indicators can provide useful information about best practices] 	Toolkit / Online book

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ROSIE project outputs @ ENERI platform] ROSIE online training course on Responsible Open Science and Citizen Science – for five different disciplinary domains (Health and Life Sciences, Humanities, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences) [link to the ENERI platform]. It can be combined with: • [ROSIE project outputs] ROSIE Knowledge Hub - materials on Responsible Open Science and Citizen Science for five different disciplinary domains (Health and Life Sciences, Humanities, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences) [link to hub] 	<p>Lectures, Case studies, Exercises, Supporting resources</p> <p>Handouts, animations & supporting information</p>
Author contribution statements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources about CRediT (CRediT website) [link] • [ROSIE project output] Acknowledging Contributions & Authorship in Open Science (Søren Holm) [link] • ReproducibiliTeach (2025, February 20). CRediT Authorship Contributor Statements [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Slides, other materials</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
Using evidence synthesis techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charité 3R – CAMARADES – Systematic Reviews - Introduction to Systematic Review & Meta-Analysis of Animal Studies [link to resource – registration for future editions] [link to workshops summary & enrollment at CAMARADES website] • Preclinical Systematic Reviews & Meta-Analysis Wiki, (August, 2025), CAMARADES Berlin, QUEST-BIH Charité. Accessed from: https://camarades.de/ • Meta-research Methods (2023, July 02). Systematic review & meta-analysis - Dr. Sarah McCann [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Online course</p> <p>Wiki & step-by-step guide</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
Preregistration or Study design plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Center for Open Science (2025, March 27). Choosing the Right Preregistration Template: A Guide for Researchers [Video]. YouTube. [link] • Center for Open Science (2020, December 09). Preregistration of Qualitative Research [Video]. YouTube. [link] • Center for Open Science (2021, March 12). Deep Dive into Open Scholarship: Preregistration and Registered Reports [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Webinar</p> <p>Webinar</p>
Registered Reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Center for Open Science (2022, March 24). Deep Dive on Open Practices: Understanding Registered Reports in Education Research [Video]. YouTube. [link] • Center for Open Science (2021, March 12). Deep Dive into Open Scholarship: Preregistration and Registered Reports [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Webinar</p> <p>Webinar</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Center for Open Science (2017, February 28). Registered Reports for Early Career Researchers [Video]. YouTube. [link] Center for Open Science (n.d.) Registered Reports. [link] 	<p>Webinar</p> <p>Workflows, Guidelines & FAQs</p>
<p>Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Röseler, L.*, Wallrich, L.*, Hartmann, H., Hüffmeier, J., Goltermann, J., Pennington, C. R., Boyce, V., Field, S. M., Pittelkow, M.-M., Silverstein, P., van Ravenzwaaij, D., Azevedo, F. (2025). Handbook for Reproduction and Replication Studies. Retrieved from [link], [DOI Zenodo] *shared first authorship FORRT Replication Database: Standardized Reproduction and Replication Templates (StaRT) [link] Meta-research Methods (2023, November 20). Replication Studies: Dr. Tim Errington [Video]. YouTube. [link] Meta-research Methods (2023, August 22). Replication studies: Dr. Olavo Amaral [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Guide</p> <p>Reporting templates</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
<p>Open step-by-step methods & protocols</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ReproducibiliTeach (2022, October 11). Report detailed methods & protocols [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2023, March 09). How to write a reusable, step-by-step protocol [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2023, March 09). How to deposit a protocol on protocols.io [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2023, March 09). How to write a PLOS One Lab Protocols article [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
<p>Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ROSiE project outputs @ The Embassy of Good Science] Quality of research outputs and data sets for citizen scientists [link to module] [ROSiE project output] Rochambeau, M., Konach, T., Bernabe, R., Bentzen, H. B., Mocheche, L. K., Dash, K. C. K., Mbanya, V., Mezinska, S., Häberlein, L., Koivisto, E., Kavouras, P., Strecht, M., Hofmann, B. M., Simm, K., Eigi.Watkin, J., Le Gall, O., Jost, F., Baraas, R., Holm, S., & Lindemann, T. (2024). ROSiE Field-specific Guidelines on Responsible Open Science. Zenodo. [DOI Zenodo] [includes specific sections for citizen science within 4 disciplinary fields - health and life sciences, humanities, natural sciences, social sciences] [ROSiE project output] ROSiE Knowledge Hub: responsible research training materials for citizen scientists [link to webpage] [ROSiE project output] ROSiE online training course on Responsible Open Science: Citizen Scientists – lectures and supporting materials [link to ENERI platform] 	<p>Module</p> <p>Guidelines</p> <p>Handouts, animations & supporting information</p> <p>Module</p> <p>Module</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ROSiE project output @ The Embassy of Good Science] Protection of Research Participants [link to module] • Balázs, B., Mooney, P., Nováková, E., Bastin, L., Jokar Arsanjani, J. (2021). Data Quality in Citizen Science. In: Vohland, K., et al. The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. [DOI] • ECS Academy: Introduction to Citizen Science [link] 	<p>Article</p> <p>Introductory course</p>
Open materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ENERI classroom resource] Biobanks [link to module] 	Module
Unique & Persistent Identifiers for research materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReproducibiliTeach (2022, October 12). Resource Research Identifiers (RRIDs) [Video]. YouTube. [link] • ReproducibiliTeach (2025, February 10). Why should I care and really need to get an ORCID? [Video]. YouTube. [link] • Digital Preservation Coalition (n.d.). Persistent Identifiers [link] 	<p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Guide</p>
Open source code & software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Research Data Alliance CURE-FAIR WG output] Arguillas, F., Christian, T.-M., Gooch, M., Honeyman, T., Peer, L., & CURE-FAIR WG. (2022). 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research (1.1). Zenodo. [DOI] 	Guide
Data sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Research Data Alliance CURE-FAIR WG output] Arguillas, F., Christian, T.-M., Gooch, M., Honeyman, T., Peer, L., & CURE-FAIR WG. (2022). 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research (1.1). Zenodo. [DOI] • [ROSiE project output @ ENERI platform] Quality of research outputs and data sets [links to specific modules: Health and Life Sciences Humanities Natural Sciences Social Sciences] • [ROSiE project output @ ENERI platform] Responsible sharing and reuse of data and other research outputs [links to specific modules: Health and Life Sciences Humanities Natural Sciences Social Sciences] • [ROSiE project output @ ENERI platform] Protection of research participants rights, persons and communities and/or cultural heritage in open science [links to specific modules: Health and Life Sciences Humanities Natural Sciences Social Sciences] • [ROSiE project output] Responsible Preparation & Management of Quantitative Datasets & Metadata (Olivier Le Gall) [link] • [ROSiE project output] Responsibility of Researchers for the Quality of the Collected, Processed & Stored Data (Panagiotis Kavouras) [link] • [ROSiE project output] Specifics of Informed Consent in the Context of Open Science (Emmi Jennina Kaaya) [link] • Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Making Qualitative Data Reusable - A Short Guidebook for 	<p>Guide</p> <p>Modules</p> <p>Modules</p> <p>Modules</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Guide</p>

	<p>Researchers and Data Stewards Working with Qualitative Data (Version 2). Zenodo. [DOI Zenodo]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Center for Open Science (2024, February 09). Sharing Sensitive Qualitative Data [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2022, October 19). Basics of Research Data Management [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2023, March 19). Creating a data dictionary [Video]. YouTube. [link] ReproducibiliTeach (2023, March 161619). How to upload a dataset into the Zenodo repository [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
Reporting of null results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [The Embassy of Good Science] Non-reporting of negative findings [link to introductory materials] 	Best practices
Reporting guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [The Embassy of Good Science] The EQUATOR Network: Reporting guidelines [link to introductory resources] ReproducibiliTeach (2022, June 11). Reporting guidelines [Video]. YouTube. [link] 	<p>Guidelines</p> <p>Video lecture</p>
Preprints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [The Embassy of Good Science] Communicate results to the general public before a peer reviewed publication is available [link to introductory notes] [The Embassy of Good Science] Preprint servers [link to introductory notes] 	<p>Best practices</p> <p>Best practices</p>
Science communication, public engagement, policy briefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality and Effectiveness in Science and Technology communication (QUEST) Science communication toolkits [link] [about] NewSera: Blueprints for science communication [particularly for Citizen Science projects] [link to toolkits] Magalhães, J., Matozinhos, K., Navalhas, I., Luís, C., Pelacho, M., Leguina, L., Elorza, A., Lacunza, I., Tola, E., & Arias, R. (2023). Guide of science communication in citizen science projects and citizen science journalism (Deliverable 5.3). Zenodo. [DOI Zenodo] 	<p>Toolkit</p> <p>Toolkit</p> <p>Guide</p>
Open educational resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abbey Elder (2019). The OER Starter Kit. Iowa State University Digital Press. [link to book, Version 1.1. Revised September 5th, 2019.] Garcia L, Batut B, Burke ML, Kuzak M, Psomopoulos F, Arcila R, et al. (2020) Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. PLoS Comput Biol 16(5): e1007854. [DOI] 	<p>Starter Kit</p> <p>Guide</p>

Legend: **CAMARADES**, Collaborative Approach to Meta Analysis and Review of Animal Experimental Studies; **CRedit**, Contributor Roles Taxonomy; **ECS**, European Citizen Science; **ENERI**, European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity; **EQUATOR**, Enhancing the Quality and Transparency of health research; **FORRT**, Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training; **OER**, Open educational resources; **pathOS**, Open Science Impact Pathways; **QUEST-BIH**, Center for Responsible Research, Berlin Institute of Health, Charité; **ROSIE**, Responsible Open Science in Europe.

Training resources listed in **Tables 1** (institutional) and **2** (external) will be shared with TREASURE participants and on the TREASURE website for those interested in applying the practices and outputs in their work, although not necessarily enrolling in the TREASURE program.

